

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

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Grape marc, a winemaking byproduct composed by the skins, seeds and pulp of grapes, constitutes an available, valuable and renewable source of bioactive ingredients such as antioxidants and dietary fibers. It is a fermentable material and induces environmental damage. Its valorization is crucial to avoid pollution and ensure sustainable development. The aim of this work is to optimize the extraction of soluble dietary fiber and to recover antioxidant phenolics from Syrah red grape marc.

A Central composite design of seventeen experiments was used to develop an optimized process allowing simultaneous extraction of dietary fibers and phenol recovery from “Syrah” grape marc. The response surface methodology was used to optimize aqueous extraction conditions of the dietary fiber based on three independent variables: temperature (80-100°C); time (30-90 min) and the grape marc/solvent ratio (1:25-1:50). The total phenolic content was recovered after soluble dietary fiber precipitation and individual phenolic compounds of the grape marc extract obtained with the best extraction conditions were identified by UHPLC-DAD-ESI/MSn. Antibacterial activity of this latter extract was evaluated against pathogenic microorganisms (two Gram + and two Gram – bacterial strains).

The statistical analyses showed that the independent variable grape marc/solvent ratio has a significant effect on the yield of soluble dietary fibers. The optimal extraction condition resulting in the highest yield of soluble dietary fibers was determined and validated. The content of total phenols of the recovered solvent was determined. UHPLC-DAD-ESI/MSn analysis of the recovered individual phenolic compounds showed the identification of 21 phenolic compounds belonging to the classes of phenolic acids, flavonoids and anthocyanins. Syrah grape marc extract showed also a potential antibacterial activity against both Gram+ and Gram- bacteria.

The findings suggest an integrated green process allowing a simultaneous recovery of dietary fibers and polyphenols from red grape marc. Recovered antioxidant and soluble dietary fibers could be use in functional food formulation and nutraceutical development.

Keywords: Red grape marc; Design of experiment; Response surface methodology; Phenolic extraction; Soluble dietary fibers; Antibacterial activity

MATHEMATICAL MODELLING OF DRYING KINETICS OF DATE SEEDS AND ASSESSMENT OF PHYTOCHEMICAL CONTENTS AND ANTIBACTERIAL POTENCY

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The date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) belongs to the palm family (*Arecaceae*), is one of the major fruit crops produced in arid and semi-arid regions of the world such as North Africa and the Middle East. The aim of this work is to determine the drying kinetics of

Tunisian Deglet Enour date seeds and the effect of drying temperature on its main phytochemical contents.

Drying kinetics of date seeds were conducted at four temperatures (50, 60, 70 and 80 °C). Eight models available in the literature were used to describe experimental drying kinetics. The statistical parameters (correlation coefficients and standard errors) showed that the approximation of diffusion model could be used to fit the experimental drying curves. The effect of the drying temperature on the phytochemicals of date seeds extract (water-acetone- ethanol, v/v/v) was also investigated. The antibacterial effect of the extract of the dried seeds was investigated.

The extract of dried date seeds at 60°C had the highest total phenols (6.6 ± 0.09 g GAE/100 g DM), total flavonoids (5.64 ± 0.14 g QE/100 g DM), total tannins (9.73 ± 0.16 g CE/100 g DM) and total carotenoid contents (0.65 ± 0.002 mg β -carotene E/100 g DM). Furthermore, the extract of date seeds dried at 60 °C shows an interesting antibacterial activity against eight foodborne pathogens. These results highlight the potential use of Tunisian date seeds as cheap, natural interesting source of bioactive and antibacterial agent.

Keywords: Date seeds; Drying; Mathematical modeling; Phytochemical contents; Antibacterial potency